

First record of *Tibitanus sexlineatus* Simon, 1907 (Araneae: Philodromidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: The genus *Tibitanus* has been recognised for the first time from South Africa from photographs. The specimen with its reddish setae forming six parallel lines over the body resembles the species *T. sexlineatus* Simon, 1907, previously recorded from Guinea-Bissau.

INTRODUCTION

Simon (1907) described the female of the genus *Tibitanus* with *T. sexlineatus* as the type species from Bolama in Guinea-Bissau, but without illustrations. *Tibitanus* resemble *Tibellus*, to which it is related, but it differs by the anterior eyes being nearly equal; the median eyes being more than three times farther apart from each other than from the lateral ones; a much narrower clypeus; long, spiniform setae present on the anterior margin; serially arranged setae on the legs; leg IV clearly shorter than leg II. From *Suemus* it differs primarily in the legs, which, as in *Tibellus*, are spiny, and the anterior metatarsi are not much shorter than the tibiae.

Lessert (1928) had reservations about *Tibitanus*. He felt the diagnostic traits of *Tibitanus* overlapped significantly with those of *Tibellus*, especially in terms of body shape, eye arrangement, and leg proportions. He felt that the differences were more likely to be intraspecific variation or adaptations rather than genus-level distinctions. However, he conceded it might still be useful as a subgenus.

Millot (1942) examined a subadult female of *T. sexlineatus* from Kindia, Guinea, and provided the first image of the body (see Fig. 6), but also listed it as a subgenus. Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994), in their revision of *Tibellus*, clearly state that it is not a member of *Tibellus*. It is also presently listed on the World Spider Catalog (2025) as a distinct genus.

Tibitanus sexlineatus was first recognised from South Africa, based on an entry in the iNaturalist data set. A female was photographed (Figs 1-5) from the Blyde River floodplain, near Hoedspruit (-24.406, 30.814) on 21 January 2022 by Wynand Uys. The spider can be recognised by the longitudinal lines formed by reddish setae present on the carapace and abdomen (Figs 1, 2 & 5). Carapace is yellowish-brown, dorsally densely covered with yellowish-white setae, with reddish setae forming six parallel lines; white, rod-shaped, blunt setae are present in the eye region (Fig. 4). Abdomen decorated with the same reddish lines (Fig. 3); it is anteriorly obtusely truncated and slightly notched and posteriorly rounded; ventrally entirely covered with white setae. Legs are the same colour as the body, but decorated with spots.

A second species *T. nomas* Simon, 1910 was described from Namibia. It differs from *T. sexlineatus* by having a shorter cephalothorax lacking red setae, and the abdomen is not marked with red lines, and the genital area is pitted and keeled.

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Figures 1–6. *Tibitanus sexlineatus* female. 1–5. A female was photographed from the Blyde River floodplain, near Hoedspruit by Wynand Uys. 6. Line drawing after Millot (1942).